

Synthesis and antiviral activity of 2-aryl-3-(substituted-benzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinones

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Abstract : A series of new heterocyclic compounds 2-aryl-3-(substituted-benzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone have been synthesized by the treatment of 3-amino-2-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinone with a substituted benzaldehyde in ethanol. All the synthesized compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectra. The synthesized compounds were screened for their antiviral activity. The compounds were found to possess moderate to good antiviral activity.

Keywords : 4(3H)-Quinazolinone, Schiff base, synthesis, antiviral activity.

Introduction

Synthesis of quinazolinone heterocycles is an attractive field for synthetic chemists due to their diverse range of pharmacological activities^{1,2}. 4(3H)-Quinazolinones occupy an important position in medicinal and pesticidal chemistry, presenting a wide range of bioactivities. As medicines, many of them display antifungal³, antimicrobial⁴, anti-HIV⁵, antitubercular⁶, anticancer⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸, anticonvulsant⁹, antidepressant¹⁰, hypolipidemic¹¹, antiulcer¹², analgesic¹³ or immunotropic activities¹⁴ and are also known to act as thymidylate synthase¹⁵, poly(ADP-ribose)polymerase (PARP)¹⁶ and protein tyrosine kinase¹⁷ inhibitors. As pesticides, they are used as insecticides¹⁸, fungicides¹⁹ and antiviral agents²⁰ such as TMV, CMV inhibitors. In light of the growing number of applications in recent years there has been an enormous increase in the interest among biologists and chemists in their synthesis and bioactivity of quinazolinone derivatives.

In the present work we have designed and synthesized a series of 2-aryl-3-(substituted-benzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone derivatives **3(a-h)** and investigated their antiviral bioactivities. The synthetic route is shown in Scheme 1. The structures of these compounds were firmly established by well defined IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass spectra and elemental analysis. Preliminary bioas-

say tests showed that some compounds displayed *in vivo* antiviral activity against TMV at 500 µg/ml. The substituents and yields of the title compounds **3(a-h)** is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Substituents and yields of title compounds **3(a-h)**

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R	Yields (%)
3a	H	Ph	4-Cl	72
3b	H	Ph	4-NO ₂	68
3c	H	Ph	4-OCH ₃	71
3d	H	Ph	4-CF ₃	75
3e	6-Br	Ph	4-Cl	73
3f	6-Br	Ph	4-NO ₂	71
3g	6-Br	Ph	4-OCH ₃	69
3h	6-Br	Ph	4-CF ₃	79

Results and discussion

The title 2-aryl-3-(substituted-benzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone compounds **3(a-h)** were synthesized by the reaction of 3-amino-2-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinone with substituted benzaldehyde in ethanol in presence of few drops of acetic acid. The structures of the compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR and mass spectra. Here we have synthesized 8 compounds and these compounds have been screened for their antiviral activity. The compounds were found to possess moderate to good antiviral activity.

The IR spectrum of compounds **3(a-h)** over the 3060–3032 cm^{-1} range showed multiple weak absorption peaks corresponding to Qu-H and Ar-H stretching vibration absorption peaks. The strong absorption peak over 1680–1670 cm^{-1} is due to C=O stretching vibration absorption and the moderate intensity absorption over 1590–1610 cm^{-1} correspond to a C=N stretching vibration. The 1591–1474 cm^{-1} absorptions are due to the skeleton vibration of the aryl and heterocyclic rings. The absorption peaks at 766 and 696 cm^{-1} arise due to the phenylsubstituted at the 2-position in the quinazolinone.

Spectral analysis shows that different pairs of carbons e.g. C-11 and C-15, C-12 and C-14, C-17 and C-21, C-18 and C-20 are attached to chemically equivalent protons. The proton attached at C-5 position appears as a multiplet at δ 7.46–7.58 ppm due to mutual coupling C4-H and C6-H. Chemical shift in the aromatic region with multiplet centered at 7.63 ppm corresponds to C4-H and the multiplet in the region 7.80–7.94 ppm arises due to the five aromatic protons present in the phenyl ring directly attached to the quinazolinone ring. The multiplet at 7.70–7.73 ppm must be for the two equivalent protons at C-11 and C-15. The singlet at 8.78–10.22 appears due to the proton attached to the imine carbon at C-9.

The chemical shifts of the quinazolinone ring carbons vary from δ 170–121.6 ppm. The carbons of phenyl ring conjugated to the imine functionality have chemical shifts in the range 127.4 to 135.4. The carbons of the unsubstituted phenyl ring directly linked to the quinazolinone ring through the intervening carbon between two ring nitrogens appear upfield 127.8–131.0 ppm.

Experimental

General : Melting points were determined using an open glass capillary method and are uncorrected. All chemicals used were of reagent grade and were used as received without further purification. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 400 MHz on a Bruker AVANCE DPX (400 MHz) FT spectrometer in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer at 70 eV. Elemental analysis were carried out using a Coleman automatic C, H and N analyzer.

Preparation of 2-aryl-4(3H)-3,1-benzoxazinone (1) ($R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{Ph}$) :

To a stirred solution of anthranilic acid (0.05 mol) in

pyridine (60 ml), benzoyl chloride (0.05 mol) was added dropwise, maintaining the temperature near 0–5 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 2 h at room temperature until a solid product was formed. The reaction mixture was neutralized with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and the pale yellow solid which separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 83%; m.p. 113–115 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3030 (C-H, Ar-H), 1721 (C=O), 1595 (C=N), 1180 (C-C); ^1H NMR : δ 7.61 (9H, m, Ar-H, quinazolinone-H); ^{13}C NMR : δ 172, 164, 154.8, 135, 131, 129, 128.6, 126.9, 124.1, 121.9 (Found : C, 75.33; H, 4.08; N, 6.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$: C, 75.32; H, 4.06; N, 6.27%); MS (FAB) m/z : 223 (M^+).

Preparation of 3-amino-2-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (2) ($R = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{Ph}$) :

To a stirred solution of **1** (0.05 mol) in pyridine (20 ml), 80% $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.15 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred and refluxed for 20 min above 100 $^\circ\text{C}$. After cooling, the crude product was obtained by filtration and recrystallized from ethanol to give product **2** as a white solid. Yield 85%; m.p. 178 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3348 (NH_2), 3030 (C-H, Ar-H), 1685 (C=O), 1598 (C=N); ^1H NMR : δ 7.92 (9H, m, Ar-H, quinazolinone-H), 5.67 (2H, s, 3-quinazolinone- NH_2), 7.48–8.19 (9H, m, Ar-H, quinazolinone-H); ^{13}C NMR : δ 161.7, 156.3, 147.2, 135.4, 134.8, 130.1, 130.0, 127.9, 126.6, 120.6 (Found : C, 70.88; H, 4.69; N, 17.71. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 70.87; H, 4.67; N, 17.71%); MS (FAB) m/z : 237 (M^+).

Preparation of Schiff base derivatives 3(a-h) :

To a solution of the appropriate substituted benzaldehyde (1.0 mmol) in ethanol (15 ml), the 3-amino-2-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (1.0 mmol) and a few drops of acetic acid (0.05 mmol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 3–8 h and the course of the reaction was monitored by TLC [(ether : ethyl acetate) 1 : 2] to its completion. The reaction mixture was cooled. The crude product was recrystallised from absolute alcohol to give the desired compounds **3(a-h)**.

Spectral data :

2-Phenyl-3-(4-chlorobenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3a) :

White solid, yield 72%, m.p. 190–192 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (cm^{-1})

Scheme 1

: ν 3059 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1680 (C=O), 1605, 1584 (C=N), 1559, 1474 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 832 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 765, 692 (monosubstituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.45–8.26 (13H, m, quinazolinone-H and Ar-H), 9.12 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170.0, 164.0, 154.7, 152.0, 136.1, 132.9, 129.9, 128.6, 127.1, 127.0, 122.1 (Found : C, 70.10; H, 3.92; N, 11.65. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$: C, 70.10; H, 3.92; N, 11.68%); MS (FAB) m/z : 359 (M^+).

2-Phenyl-3-(4-nitrobenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3b) :

White solid, yield 68%, m.p. 208–210 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3057 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1681 (C=O), 1605, 1589 (C=N), 1568–1445 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 830 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 768, 692 (monosubstituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.28–8.26 (13H, m, quinazolinone-H and Ar-H), 9.31 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170.0, 164.0, 154.7, 152.0, 150.7, 137.3, 132.9, 129.9, 128.6, 127.1, 127.0, 125.9, 122.1 (Found : C, 68.06; H,

3.79; N, 15.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 68.10; H, 3.81; N, 15.13%); MS (FAB) m/z : 370 (M^+).

2-Phenyl-3-(4-methoxybenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3c) :

White solid, yield 71%, m.p. 193–195 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3060 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1684 (C=O), 1614, 1597 (C=N), 1577, 1468 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 1275, 1088 (Ar-O-CH₃), 840 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 765, 690 (monosubstituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.42–8.26 (13H, m, Qu-H and Ar-H), 9.29 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 167.7, 164.0, 154.7, 133.2, 132.9, 130.0, 129.9, 128.6, 127.1, 127.0, 122.1, 114.2 (Found : C, 74.34; H, 4.81; N, 11.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 74.35; H, 4.82; N, 11.82%); MS (FAB) m/z : 355 (M^+).

2-Phenyl-3-(4-trifluoromethylbenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3d) :

White solid, yield 75%, m.p. 196–198 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) :

ν 3056 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1682 (C=O), 1605, 1585 (C=N), 1556–1475 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 836 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 768, 692 (monosubstituted benzene); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.42–8.22 (13H, m, Qu-H, Ar-H), 9.18 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170.0, 164.0, 154.7, 152.0, 134.5, 133.3, 133.2, 129.9, 128.6, 127.1, 125.4, 122.1 (Found : C, 67.15; H, 3.56; N, 10.66. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{14}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 67.17; H, 3.59; N, 10.68%); MS (FAB) m/z : 393 (M^+).

6-Bromo-2-phenyl-3-(4-chlorobenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3e) :

White solid, yield 73%, m.p. 205–207 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3061 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1684 (C=O), 1603, 1587 (C=N), 1551–1445 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 843 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 768, 690 (monosubstituted benzene), 675 (Qu-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.42–8.28 (13H, m, quinazolinone-H and Ar-H), 9.48 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170, 164, 154.7, 151, 136.5, 132.9, 131.9, 130.4, 129.9, 129.0, 128.6, 125.9, 124.3, 121.7 (Found : C, 57.47; H, 2.97; N, 9.56. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrClN}_3\text{O}$: C, 57.49; H, 2.99; N, 9.58%); MS (FAB) m/z : 438 (M^+).

6-Bromo-2-phenyl-3-(4-nitrobenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3f) :

White solid, yield 71%, m.p. 277–279 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3060 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1681 (C=O), 1600, 1585 (C=N), 1548, 1440 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 815 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 765, 685 (monosubstituted benzene), 680 (Qu-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.49–8.26 (13H, m, quinazolinone-H and Ar-H), 9.51 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170, 164, 154.7, 151.0, 150.7, 137.3, 136.5, 132.9, 129.9, 129.2, 125.9, 124.3 (Found : C, 56.48; H, 2.90; N, 12.48. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrN}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 56.49; H, 2.92; N, 12.50%); MS (FAB) m/z : 449 (M^+).

6-Bromo-2-phenyl-3-(4-methoxybenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3g) :

White solid, yield 69%, m.p. 217–219 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3061 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1685 (C=O), 1610, 1580 (C=N), 1547–1443 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 842 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 765, 685 (monosubstituted benzene), 679 (Qu-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.42–8.26 (13H, m, quinazolinone-H and Ar-H), 9.45 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170, 164.3, 164, 151.0, 136.5, 131.9,

130.0, 129.9, 129.2, 128.6, 125.9, 124.3, 114.2 (Found : C, 60.82; H, 3.69; N, 9.66. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 60.84; H, 3.71; N, 9.68%); MS (FAB) m/z : 434 (M^+).

6-Bromo-2-phenyl-3-(4-trifluorobenzalamino)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3h) :

White solid, yield 79%, m.p. 184–186 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : ν 3060 (Qu-H, Ar-H), 1685 (C=O), 1605–1580 (C=N), 1545–1445 (C=C, benzene and quinazolinone rings), 840 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 769–685 (monosubstituted benzene), 680 (Qu-Br); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 7.45–8.21 (13H, m, Qu-H and Ar-H), 9.49 (1H, s, Qu-N=CH-Ar); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 170, 164, 151.0, 136.5, 134.5, 133, 132.9, 129.9, 129.3, 128.6, 125.9, 125.4, 121.7 (Found : C, 55.94; H, 2.75; N, 8.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrF}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 55.95; H, 2.77; N, 8.90%); MS (FAB) m/z : 472 (M^+).

Antiviral activity :

The *in vivo* bioassay results against TMV are given in Table 2. Ningnanmycin was used as reference antiviral agent. The compound **3d** and **3h** show more antiviral activity than the other compounds. Presence of 4- CF_3 as R enhance the activity rate than other substituents.

Table 2. The antiviral activity of the synthesized compounds **3(a-h)**

Agents	Concentration (mg/L)	Inhibition rate (%)
Ningnanmycin	500	53.5
3a	500	44.7
3b	500	25.3
3c	500	43.2
3d	500	52.9
3e	500	42.8
3f	500	43
3g	500	38.9
3h	500	52.1

The leaves of *Nicotiana tabacum* growing at the same ages were selected. The tobacco mosaic virus with the concentration of 6×10^{-3} mg/ml was dipped and inoculated on the whole leaves. Then the leaves were washed with water and dried. The compound solution was smeared on the right side for control. The local lesion numbers were then recorded 3–4 days after inoculation²¹. For each compound, the times of repetition were conducted to ensure the reliability of the results.

Inhibition rate (%) = av. local lesion numbers of control (not treated with compound) – av. local lesion numbers smeared with drugs/av. local lesion numbers without drugs.

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